

THE GROWING CONNECTION BETWEEN GUT AND MENTAL HEALTH

by

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Abstract

The growing branch of research focusing on the connection between gut and mental health, has indicated a strong link between these two variables through the microbiota-gut-brain axis. In order to really understand the microbiota-gut-brain axis, one needs to focus on the components that form this three-factor link. The microbiota, or human microbiome, consists of symbiotic cells that have many roles in the human body. Illnesses arise when there is an imbalance, or dysbiosis, of these cells. The vagus nerve connects everything an individual eats to the brain, making it the main form of communication between these two seemingly separate parts of the body. Lastly, the enteric nervous system controls gastrointestinal behavior separately from the central nervous system. Evidence has shown that this three-factor link affects an individual's behavior and emotional well-being. The purpose of this paper is to further discuss this growing connection of gut and mental health, by presenting past research as well as my own research. My research consisted of a 17 question survey, where individuals were asked their diets and mental health state in the span of 2 weeks. The results were analyzed in order to determine if there was a correlation between higher scores in the diet questionnaire (more than half the days and nearly every day) and higher scores in the Patient Health Questionnaire-9 scale (PHQ-9), created by Dr. Kurt Kroenke. Results showed a significant correlation between five diet variables and higher scores on the PHQ-9 scale.

The Growing Connection Between Gut and Mental Health

Past research has focused on established values that are known to underlie mental health, such as childhood experiences, relationships, lifestyle, family history, genetics, etc. While some widely accepted practices have focused on treating mental health patients with psychotropic's, concentrating on treating the symptoms rather than the cause. For the past two years, I have researched and explored the growing connection between the microbial world of the gut and mental health. This growing branch of research has indicated a strong link between gut health and an individual's emotional well-being, particularly depression (Dawson et al. 2016). New literature on this topic continues to show that the state of an individual's gut plays an important role in their mental health. This has caused a major shift in the way researchers and medical professionals have begun to approach mental health. In this paper, I focus on this growing connection by reviewing past research on this topic and presenting my own research. The purpose of this paper can be summarized into three parts. First, I will be providing information about the key aspects of the gut microbiome. Second, I will be presenting my research and results. Third, I will be further discussing my results and its relation to past research, as well as future indications on this topic.

Background Information

The human microbiome consists of about 10-100 trillion symbiotic microbial cells, primarily located in the gut (Ursell et al. 2013). Symbiotic microbial cells

outnumber human cells ten to one and their purpose is to help digest the food individual's eat, regulate the immune system, protect individuals against other bacteria that cause disease, and produce vitamins. These microbial cells have co-evolved with humans, interacting with an individual's body in an intricate and balanced way. When there is an imbalance, or dysbiosis, health problems can arise. Imbalances can occur from illnesses, poor diet, a course of antibiotics, and other factors that ultimately cause changes to these cells (Hair & Shapre, 2014). These causes, or factors, can lead to psychiatric and behavioral problems since the brain and gut are connected through the vagus nerve.

The vagus nerve is the main form of communication between two seemingly separate parts of the body, the gut and the brain. Everything an individual eats is directly linked to the brain through the vagus nerve. The vagus nerve is crucial to several bodily functions, including control of mood, immune response, digestion, and heart rate (Breit et. al. 2018). Even if the vagus nerve was severed, or cut, the gut would continue to function since the human gut is the only organ to have its own nervous system that functions separately from the autonomic nervous system.

The enteric nervous system, located in the gut, controls gastrointestinal behavior separately from the central nervous system. The enteric nervous system is often called the "second brain" secondary to having more neurons than the peripheral nervous system, having similar cells to the brain, and producing 50% of dopamine and 90% of serotonin. These components create the microbiota-gut-brain axis connection. The microbiota-gut

brain axis has a role to integrate and monitor the gut, while also linking the cognitive and emotional centers of the brain with peripheral intestinal functions (Carabotti et al. 2019). Evidence suggests that this three-factor link, the microbiota-gut-brain axis, affects an individual's behavior, disease, and emotional experience.

Research Methods

The participants in this study were voluntarily collected through social media and SONA systems, including people ages 18-55+. There were a total of 146 participants who participated in the survey, but only 122 participants were used for the final data analysis. The participants who were not used for the final data analysis did not complete the entire length of the survey.

The survey consisted of four sections, with a total of 17 questions. The first section was the consent form, stating that all participants must be over the age of 18, agree to participate in the study, and live in the United States. The second section collected non-identifying socio-demographic information of each participant. The third section gathered participant's specific diets over the course of two weeks. These questions were created in order to ask participants how often they had eaten foods or drank beverages that were good or bad for optimal gut health, based on prior research. Each question had four options for an answer: Not at all (+0), several days (+1), more than half the days (+2), and nearly every day (+3). Foods that are bad for optimal gut health were graded positively on the scale and foods that are good for optimal gut health

were reverse scored on SPSS. Therefore, participants with a higher overall score had a higher frequency in eating foods that were bad for gut health and a higher frequency in a lack of eating foods that were good for gut health. The fourth section was the PHQ-9, created by Dr. Kurt Kroenke, which is used to objectify the degree of depression severity in the participants. Each question had four options for an answer: Not at all (+0), several days (+1), more than half the days (+2), and nearly every day (+3).

After answering all of the questions, a score from the PHQ-9 was calculated for every participant. A score of less than or equal to 4 suggested minimal depression, scores of 5-9 suggested mild depression, scores of 10-14 suggested moderate to severe depression, and a score of 20 or greater suggested severe depression.

The results of the survey were then analyzed using SPSS Statistics by performing a Pearson's R correlation test. A Pearson's R correlation was used in order to measure the statistical relationship, or association, between the participant's diet in the span of two weeks and their mental health state. Specifically, I analyzed if there was a correlation between higher scores in the diet questionnaire (more than half the days and nearly every day) and higher scores in the PHQ-9 scale. A significant positive correlation would indicate that eating or drinking foods that are bad for optimal gut health, for more than half the days or nearly every day for 2 weeks, is positively correlated to a higher score on the PHQ-9 scale.

Results

From the 122 participants, 110 participants were ages 18-23, 7 participants were ages 24-30, 1 participant was 31-36, 1 participant was 37-42, 2 were 43-48, and 1 participant was 49-54. In terms of marital status, 5 identified as married, 13 identified as in a partnership, and 104 identified as single. For occupation, 4 identified as manual workers/technicians, 12 identified as mid-level workers, 5 identified as self-employed, 97 identified as students, and 4 identified as white collar/executive employees.

A total of 122 scores were analyzed from the PHQ-9 scale. Zero participants scored between the scores 0-4, which suggests zero to minimal depression. Four participants scored between the scores 5-9, which suggests mild depression. Thirty-nine participants scored between the scores 10-14, which suggests moderate depression. Forty-nine participants scored between the scores 15-19, which suggests moderately severe depression. Thirty participants scored 20+, which suggests severe depression.

After performing a Pearson's R correlation test between every variable in the diet section and every variable in the PHQ-9 section, there were five diet variables that had a significant positive correlation with a variable from the PHQ-9 scale.

Drinking alcoholic beverages, more than half the days or nearly every day for two weeks, was seen to have a significant correlation with "feeling tired or having little energy," more than half the days or nearly every day for 2 weeks. There was a .016 significance, meaning that the correlation was significant at the 0.05 level.

Figure 1

Pearson’s R Correlation Test for Alcoholic Beverages and “Feeling Tired or Having Little Energy”

Correlations

		alcbev	tired
alcbev	Pearson Correlation	1	-.216*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.016
	N	125	125
tired	Pearson Correlation	-.216*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.016	
	N	125	125

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Eating processed foods, more than half the days or nearly every day for 2 weeks, was seen to have a significant correlation with “feeling down, depressed, or hopeless,” more than half the days or nearly every day for 2 weeks. There was a 0.047 significance, meaning that the correlation was significant at the 0.05 level.

Figure 2

Pearson’s R Correlation Test for Processed Foods and “Feeling Down, Depressed, or Hopeless”

Correlations

		procfo	dep
procfo	Pearson Correlation	1	.178*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.047
	N	125	125
dep	Pearson Correlation	.178*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.047	
	N	125	125

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Eating processed foods, more than half the days or nearly every day for 2 weeks, was also seen to have a significant correlation with “moving or speaking so slowly that other people could have noticed, or so fidgety or restless that you have been moving a lot more than usual” more than half the days or nearly every day for 2 weeks. There was a 0.021 significance, meaning that the correlation was significant at the 0.05 level.

Figure 3

Pearson's R Correlation Test for Processed Foods and “Moving or Speaking So Slowly That Other People Could Have Noticed, or So Fidgety or Restless That You Have Been Moving a Lot More Than Usual”

Correlations

		procfo	slowfidg
procfo	Pearson Correlation	1	.206*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.021
	N	125	125
slowfidg	Pearson Correlation	.206*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.021	
	N	125	125

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

The lack of eating foods containing unsaturated fats more than half the days or nearly every day for 2 weeks, was seen to have a significant correlation with “little interest or pleasure in doing things,” more than half the days or nearly every day for 2 weeks. There was a 0.030 significance, meaning that the correlation was significant at the 0.05 level.

Figure 4.

Pearson’s R Correlation Test for Lack of Foods Containing Unsaturated Fats and “Little Interest or Pleasure in Doing Things”

Correlations

		unsatfat	int
unsatfat	Pearson Correlation	1	-.194*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.030
	N	125	125
int	Pearson Correlation	-.194*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.030	
	N	125	125

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

The lack of eating foods containing unsaturated fats more than half the days or nearly every day for 2 weeks, was also seen to have a significant correlation with “feeling down, depressed, or hopeless,” more than half the days or nearly every day for 2 weeks. There was a 0.027 significance, meaning that the correlation was significant at the 0.05 level.

Figure 5

Pearson's R Correlation Test for Lack of Foods Containing Unsaturated Fats and “Feeling Down, Depressed, or Hopeless”

Correlations

		unsatfat	dep
unsatfat	Pearson Correlation	1	-.198*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.027
	N	125	125
dep	Pearson Correlation	-.198*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.027	
	N	125	125

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

The lack of eating fermented foods more than half the days or nearly every day for 2 weeks, was seen to have a significant correlation with “feeling down, depressed, or hopeless” more than half the days or nearly every day for 2 weeks. There was a 0.044 significance, meaning that correlation was significant at the 0.05 level.

Figure 6

Pearson's R Correlation Test for Lack of Fermented Foods and “Feeling Down, Depressed, or Hopeless”

Correlations

		ferfoo	dep
ferfoo	Pearson Correlation	1	-.180*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.044
	N	125	125
dep	Pearson Correlation	-.180*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.044	
	N	125	125

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

The lack of eating leafy greens more than half the days or nearly every day for 2 weeks, was seen to have a significant correlation with “trouble concentrating on things, such as reading or watching television” more than half the days or nearly every day for 2 weeks. There was a 0.020 significance, meaning that the correlation as significant at the 0.05 level.

Figure 7

Pearson’s R Correlation Test for Lack of Leafy Greens and “Trouble Concentrating On Things, Such As Reading or Watching Television.”

Correlations

		leaf	conc
leaf	Pearson Correlation	1	-.208*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.020
	N	125	125
conc	Pearson Correlation	-.208*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.020	
	N	125	125

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

The lack of eating foods more than half the days or nearly every day for 2 weeks containing prebiotics, showed no significant correlation to a higher score on a variable in the PHQ-9 scale. Eating foods containing artificial sweeteners or saturated fats more than half the days or nearly every day for 2 weeks, also showed no significant correlation to a higher score on any variable in the PHQ-9 scale.

Discussion

The results of my study support current literature on this topic. When focusing on the connection between gut health and depression, there is evidence that patients with depression have compositional gut microbiome differences than those of healthy controls (Butler et al., 2019). These compositional differences can result from dietary impacts on the gut microbiome. Foods that have been seen to benefit gut health include probiotics, prebiotics, unsaturated fats, leafy greens, and fermented foods. These foods are able to

benefit gut health by producing beneficial bacteria, such as Bifidobacterium and Lactobacillus (Canesso et al. 2014).

Alcohol and Depression

My results showed that drinking alcohol beverages more than half the days or nearly every day for two weeks were associated with higher scores on the PHQ-9, specifically on feeling tired or having little energy. These results agree with current literature on this topic that show that those who showed signs of intestinal permeability, from alcohol consumption, had higher scores on measures of depression, anxiety, and alcohol cravings (Leclercq et al. 2012). The reason for this relationship is due to alcohol consumption leading to the inflammation of the GI tract, which causes an overgrowth of bacteria in the gut (Bishehsari et al. 2017). This leads to a disruption, or dysbiosis, of the microbiome which results in a lack of growth of beneficial bacteria.

Processed Foods and Depression

Processed foods have been shown to increase bacterial translocation, or changes, altering the microbiota of an individual (Rhodes, 2021). This promotes dysbiosis to occur, resulting in illnesses such as depression. The results indicated that eating processed foods more than half the days or nearly every day for 2 weeks was associated with a higher score on the PHQ-9 scale, specifically in feeling down, depressed, or hopeless and being fidgety or slow. The state of dysbiosis in the gut microbiota from eating processed foods generate unhealthy signals to the brain. These unhealthy signals

can be manifested as an increase in oxidative stress, increase in cellular degradation, inflammation, and unbalanced energy homeostasis. Evidence suggests that this pathology contributes to depression (González Olmo et al. 2021).

Unsaturated Fats and Depression

In terms of fats, there are differences in microbiota between those who have an intake of high saturated fat diet versus a high unsaturated fat diet. Those who had a high saturated fat diet showed a greater amount of *Bacteroides*, *Bilophila*, and *Faecalibacterium prausnitzii* in their gut microbiome. Those who had a high unsaturated fat diet showed a great amount of *Bifidobacteria*, *Lactobacillus*, *Streptococcus*, and *Akkermansia muciniphila* (Singh et al. 2017). These differences in the gut microbiome can produce profound effects on the overall health of an individual, specifically their mental health state. As seen in the results, those who lacked eating foods containing unsaturated fats were seen to have higher scores in the PHQ-9 scale, specifically in feeling down, depressed, or hopeless and feeling fidgety or moving slow. A lack of unsaturated fats in one's diet can lead to microbial differences in the gut, which result in a depletion of beneficial bacteria.

Fermented Foods and Depression

A lack of fermented foods in one's diet was seen to have a significant relationship with a higher score on the PHQ-9 scale, specifically in feeling down, depressed, or hopeless. The lack of fermented foods causes a lack of *Bifidobacteria* and *Lactobacilli*,

both of which are beneficial to the gut and are seen in healthy individuals (Singh et al. 2017). Depleting the body of these beneficial bacteria can promote dysbiosis in the gut microbiota, causing illness in an individual's health.

Future Indications

Although my results found a significant relationship between diet variables and variables on the PHQ-9 scale, the relationship found was purely correlational. There are many other variables that could affect an individual's mental health state, and those variables were not accounted for in this study; therefore, my results did not show direct causation.

With the population becoming progressively more reliant on poor-quality and highly-processed foods, there is now a growing concern for an increase in mental disorders. The microbiota-gut-brain axis has been seen to be a key between this link, where diet plays an important role in the health of the gut. An individual's diet composes the gut microbiome, either depleting or building beneficial bacteria in their gut. Beneficial bacteria can be built, or grown, by relying on a nutrient-rich diet that is optimal for gut health. A depletion of beneficial bacteria is caused by a lack of a nutrient-rich diet that is optimal for gut health. Researchers are now trying to further understand this relationship, in order to develop solutions for patients dealing with depression. Future research on the growing connection between gut and mental health can be the key to a new solution in treating patients with mental health disorders.

References

- Bishehsari, F., Magno, E., Swanson, G., Desai, V., Voigt, R. M., Forsyth, C. B., & Keshavarzian, A. (2017). Alcohol and Gut-Derived Inflammation. *Alcohol research : current reviews*, 38(2), 163–171.
- Dawson, S. L., Dash, S. R., & Jacka, F. N. (2016). The Importance of Diet and Gut Health to the Treatment and Prevention of Mental Disorders. *International review of neurobiology*, 131, 325–346. <https://doi.org/10.1016/bs.irn.2016.08.009>
- González Olmo, B. M., Butler, M. J., & Barrientos, R. M. (2021). Evolution of the Human Diet and Its Impact on Gut Microbiota, Immune Responses, and Brain Health. *Nutrients*, 13(1), 196. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nu13010196>
- Hair, M., & Sharpe, J. (2014). Fast facts about the human microbiome. The Human Microbiome. Retrieved April 13, 2022, from https://depts.washington.edu/ceeh/downloads/FF_Microbiome.pdf
- Leclercq, S., De Saeger, C., Delzenne, N., de Timary, P., & Stärkel, P. (2014). Role of inflammatory pathways, blood mononuclear cells, and gut-derived bacterial products in alcohol dependence. *Biological psychiatry*, 76(9), 725–733. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biopsych.2014.02.003>
- M C C, C., N L, L., C M, F., J L, G., D, A., C, G., G, C., S H, P., C, M., F S, M., J R, N., M M, T., A L B, G., & A T, V. (2014). Comparing the effects of acute alcohol consumption in germ-free and conventional mice: the role of the gut

microbiota. *BMC microbiology*, 14, 240. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12866-014-0240-4>

Rhodes, J. M. (2021). Nutrition and gut health: the impact of specific dietary components- it's not just five-a-day. *Proceedings of the Nutrition Society*, 80(1), 9-18. <https://doi-org.lib-proxy.fullerton.edu/10.1017/S0029665120000026>

Singh, R. K., Chang, H. W., Yan, D., Lee, K. M., Ucmak, D., Wong, K., Abrouk, M., Farahnik, B., Nakamura, M., Zhu, T. H., Bhutani, T., & Liao, W. (2017). Influence of diet on the gut microbiome and implications for human health. *Journal of translational medicine*, 15(1), 73. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12967-017-1175-y>

Ursell, L. K., Metcalf, J. L., Parfrey, L. W., & Knight, R. (2012). Defining the human microbiome. *Nutrition reviews*, 70 Suppl 1(Suppl 1), S38–S44. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1753-4887.2012.00493.x>

Verdino, J. (2017). The third tier in treatment: Attending to the growing connection between gut health and emotional well-being. *Health Psychology Open*, 4(2). <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3426293/>